

EVALUATION OF THE IMPACT RESISTANCE OF REINFORCED CARBON-CARBON

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ABSTRACT

Results of hypervelocity impact (HVI) tests conducted at the Johnson Space Center Hypervelocity Impact Test Facility (HIT-F) on reinforced carbon-carbon (RCC) samples are presented. The RCC test specimens are representative of RCC components used on the Space Shuttle Orbiter. The objectives of the HVI testing were to determine impact damage characteristics of the RCC, establish the threshold of particular damage modes such as coating damage and complete penetration of the RCC sample, and to develop correlations for predicting impact damage. In addition, numerical modeling of hypervelocity impact effects on coated RCC samples was completed using hydrocode simulations.

Key words: Hypervelocity Impact, Orbital Debris and Meteoroid Impact Effects, Reinforced Carbon-Carbon, Damage Modes, Numerical Simulations

Nomenclature

d	projectile diameter (cm)	t	thickness (cm)
ρ	density (g/cm^3)	Θ	impact angle measured from surface normal (deg)
P	penetration depth (cm)	V	Projectile velocity (km/sec)

Subscripts:

p	projectile
t	target (RCC)

1. INTRODUCTION

Reinforced Carbon-Carbon (RCC) is a structural composite used as the thermal protection system (TPS) for the high temperature areas of reusable space vehicles such as the Space Shuttle Orbiter. Resistance to damage by foreign object impact has received considerable attention on the Orbiter TPS. Due to the brittle nature of the RCC silicon carbide coating and the requirement to maintain oxidation protection, the effect of impact damage on the mission life and structural performance of the RCC components is of concern. Impact damage may occur from a variety of threats with a wide range of impact speeds. Meteoroids and man-made orbital debris represent a source of high-velocity impact damage to spacecraft structures [1], while other sources of damage include handling and service damage, launch debris, and runway debris from landing. Orbital debris can impact orbiting spacecraft at speeds from less than 1 km/sec to over 14 km/sec, and meteoroids from 10 km/sec to over 70 km/sec [1].

The effects of impact damage on the RCC material have been investigated experimentally with the objective of establishing damage threshold values. Specifically, high speed impact tests have been conducted at the Johnson Space Center (JSC) HIT-F to establish damage threshold, damage characteristics, and develop correlations for predicting impact damage. The objective of this paper is to describe these tests, present test results and correlations.

2. TEST ARTICLES

Test articles consisted of silicon-carbide (SiC) coated reinforced carbon-carbon samples shown in Figure 1. Nominal thickness of the RCC samples is 6.3 mm. These samples are representative of RCC components on the Space Shuttle Orbiter, which include the nose cap, wing leading edge panels, an area between the nose landing gear door and nose cap, and a small area surrounding the forward attach fitting of the external tank to the Orbiter.

Figure 1. RCC Test Article Dimensions (Typical).

The test sample substrate is an all-carbon composite laminate fabricated in a multiple pyrolysis and densification process from a 19 ply phenolic-graphite layup [2,3]. The substrate has a density of 1.44 g/cm^3 to 1.6 g/cm^3 (90 lb/ft^3 to 100 lb/ft^3) and is typically 4.3 mm to 5.3 mm thick.

The oxidation-resistant SiC coating is formed in a diffusion reaction process. It is typically 0.5 mm to 1.0 mm thick. Further oxidation resistance is provided by impregnation with tetraethyl-orthosilicate (TEOS) that when cured, leaves a silicon dioxide (SiO_2) residue throughout the coating and substrate. Any porosity or microcracks exposing carbon are filled by an application of a surface sealant (sodium silicate/SiC mixture) in the final step of the fabrication process. More details on the development and fabrication of the Orbiter RCC applications are given by Curry et al. [2,3].

3. TEST PROCEDURE

Hypervelocity impact tests were performed in the JSC Hypervelocity Impact Test Facility (HIT-F) using 1.7 mm, 4.3 mm, and 12.5 mm, two-stage, light-gas guns [4]. The HVI tests were designed to investigate thresholds for several damage modes to the coated RCC samples. These are shown in Figure 2 as complete penetration of the surface coating (transition from Damage Mode A to B), the on-set of rear-side spall damage (Damage Mode C), and complete penetration of the RCC sample (Damage Mode D).

Figure 2. Coated RCC Damage Modes.

Table 1 lists the HVI test conditions. Spherical projectiles from 0.06 cm to 0.32 cm diameter were launched at RCC with speeds from 2.36 km/sec to 7.52 km/sec. The majority of the tests utilized

aluminum alloy (2017-T4) projectiles, although tests were conducted with nylon and steel projectiles to assess projectile density effects. Oblique impact effects were investigated by varying impact angle from normal to the surface (0°) to highly oblique angles (89°).

HIT-F diagnostic equipment such as ultra-high speed framing cameras were used in the tests to insure the integrity of the projectile prior to impact and to verify the velocity of impact. Further details and examples of the high-speed camera film can be found elsewhere [4].

Table 1. Hypervelocity Impact Test Conditions.

Projectile Parameters								Target Parameters	
JSC HIT-F Shot Number	Projectile Material	Projectile Shape	Projectile Size* (mm)	Projectile Density (g/cm ³)	Projectile Mass (mg)	Projectile Velocity (km/sec)	Impact Angle (degrees)	RCC Thickness** (mm)	RCC Density (g/cm ³)
JSC-A1586	Al 2017-T4	sphere	3.17	2.796	46.80	6.14	89.5	0.63	1.62
JSC-A1589	Al 2017-T4	sphere	3.17	2.796	46.80	6.24	89	0.63	1.62
JSC-A1591	Al 2017-T4	sphere	3.18	2.796	46.90	6.12	89	0.63	1.62
JSC-A1587	Al 2017-T4	sphere	3.17	2.796	46.80	6.24	89	0.63	1.62
JSC-A1590	Al 2017-T4	sphere	3.17	2.796	46.80	6.03	89	0.63	1.62
JSC-2043	Al 2017-T4	sphere	1.59	2.796	5.93	5.03	65	0.57	1.54
JSC-2047	Al 2017-T4	cylinder	1.52 x 1.15	2.796	5.87	5.17	75	0.57	1.54
JSC-2301	Al 2017-T4	sphere	0.61	2.796	0.33	6.72	0	0.63	1.62
JSC-2316	Al 2017-T4	sphere	0.80	2.796	0.74	6.84	0	0.63	1.62
JSC-2322	Al 2017-T4	sphere	0.80	2.796	0.75	7.33	45	0.63	1.62
JSC-A1550	Al 2017-T4	sphere	3.17	2.796	46.64	6.28	80	0.70	1.62
JSC-A1593	Al 2017-T4	sphere	3.17	2.796	46.80	6.35	86	0.63	1.62
JSC-A1594	Al 2017-T4	sphere	3.18	2.796	46.90	6.25	84	0.63	1.62
JSC-A1595	Al 2017-T4	sphere	3.18	2.796	46.90	6.30	82	0.63	1.62
JSC-A1825	Al 2017-T4	sphere	0.99	2.796	1.40	5.93	0	0.63	1.62
JSC-2327	Al 2017-T4	sphere	0.80	2.796	0.76	7.45	55	0.63	1.62
JSC-2328	Nylon	sphere	1.21	1.14	1.05	7.52	0	0.63	1.62
JSC-A1827	Al 2017-T4	sphere	1.25	2.796	2.85	5.94	0	0.63	1.62
JSC-A1575	C-Steel	sphere	3.16	7.86	130.17	2.49	88	0.63	1.62
JSC-A1571	C-Steel	sphere	3.16	7.86	130.06	2.48	80	0.63	1.62
JSC-A1572	C-Steel	sphere	3.16	7.86	129.89	2.36	85	0.63	1.62

* Projectile Size: diameter for spheres, diameter x length for cylinders

** RCC SIC Coating Thickness: 0.76-1.02 mm for all shots except JSC-2043 and JSC-2047 RCC coating with thickness 0.2-0.4 mm

4. TEST RESULTS

Table 2 lists data from the measurement of damage to the RCC samples observed after the HVI tests. Damage was measured on both front and rear surfaces and included the depth of penetration (if the sample was not completely penetrated), the extent of coating damage, and the extent of exposed carbon substrate where the coating was completely removed. Figure 3 illustrates these measurements.

Table 2. RCC Damage Data.

JSC HIT-F Shot Number	Damage Mode	RCC Front Side				RCC Rear Side			
		Penetration Depth (mm)	Exposed RCC (mm)	Coating Damage (mm)	Hole Size (mm)	Coating Damage (mm)	Exposed RCC (mm)	Depth of Spall* (mm)	
JSC-A1586	Surface Coating Damage	0.40	0	26.0 x 4.0	0	0	0	0	
JSC-A1589	Surface Coating Damage	0.40	0	28.0 x 4.0	0	0	0	0	
JSC-A1591	Surface Coating Damage	0.50	0	26.0 x 5.0	0	0	0	0	
JSC-A1587	RCC Penetration	0.70	2.0 x 1.0	25.0 x 7.0	0	0	0	0	
JSC-A1590	RCC Penetration	0.90	4.0 x 2.0	16.0 x 6.0	0	0	0	0	
JSC-2043	Rear-Side Spall	2.40	5.2 x 4.3	8.7 x 8.5	0	11.0 x 10.0	11.0 x 10.0	2.80	
JSC-2047	Rear-Side Spall	1.30	5.6 x 4.9	8.3 x 8.1	0	7.8 x 6.8	-	-	
JSC-2301	Rear-Side Spall	1.60	2.6 x 2.6	7.5 x 6.4	0	7.1 x 6.9	0	0.10	
JSC-2316	Rear-Side Spall	2.02	3.8 x 3.5	9.6 x 9.9	0	9.5 x 8.9	4.9 x 5.5	0.80	
JSC-2322	Rear-Side Spall	2.10	2.5 x 2.9	9.6 x 9.4	0	6.7 x 6.6	2.6 x 3.7	1.20	
JSC-A1550	Rear-Side Spall	3.10	9.0 x 6.0	11.0 x 10.5	0	25.0 x 17.0	23.0 x 14.0	3.00	
JSC-A1593	Rear-Side Spall	1.40	3.0 x 3.0	24.0 x 9.0	0	11.0 x 10.0	10.0 x 7.0	0.80	
JSC-A1594	Rear-Side Spall	1.40	12.0 x 9.0	18.0 x 9.0	0	8.0 x 5.0	5.0 x 3.0	0.90	
JSC-A1595	Rear-Side Spall	3.10	9.1 x 6.8	13.6 x 12.2	0	16.5 x 14.6	11.9 x 9.8	2.10	
JSC-A1825	Rear-Side Spall	2.80	6.0 x 7.3	11.1 x 13.0	0	9.3 x 10.4	5.0 x 5.1	2.90	
JSC-2327	Rear-Side Spall	1.70	2.9 x 2.4	7.1 x 6.5	0	8.1 x 3.5	4.8 x 3.5	0.90	
JSC-2328	Rear-Side Spall	2.60	4.8 x 4.5	9.1 x 11.0	0	12.5 x 13.0	8.3 x 9.7	0.80	
JSC-A1827	Perforation	6.30	10.4 x 8.1	16.6 x 14.0	2.9 x 3.1	15.6 x 17.0	11.3 x 12.8	-	
JSC-A1575	Rear-Side Spall (Steel)	2.10	13.0 x 5.0	20.0 x 10.0	0	18.0 x 14.0	17.0 x 11.0	0.90	
JSC-A1571	Perforation (Steel)	6.30	13.0 x 11.0	17.0 x 19.0	9.0 x 6.5	20.0 x 19.0	16.0 x 15.0	-	
JSC-A1572	Perforation (Steel)	6.30	10.0 x 7.0	18.0 x 13.0	3.4 x 2.7	21.0 x 16.0	18.0 x 14.0	-	

* Note: Depth of Rear-Side Spall includes thickness of lost coating plus any RCC substrate lost.

Figure 3. RCC Damage Definitions.

Figure 4 shows the result of a 0.8 mm diameter aluminum sphere impacting the RCC sample at 6.84 km/sec normal to the surface (HIT-F Shot 2316). Because the SiC coating is brittle, the coating is damaged in an area around the impact site over 10 times larger than the projectile diameter. The broken coating on the front exposes the RCC substrate over an area 4 times larger than the projectile diameter. The front side of the RCC is penetrated to a depth ~2.5 times the projectile diameter. The coating on the rear side of the RCC sample is also damaged in a wide area, approximately the same as on front, with the RCC substrate exposed to ~6.5 projectile diameters.

Tables 1 and 2 indicate that a similar 0.8 mm diameter projectile that impacts at a 55° oblique angle (Shot JSC-2327) results in less penetration into the front of the RCC and less rear-side spall.

Figure 4. JSC HIT-F Shot 2316: 0.8 mm Al 2017T4 projectile at 6.84 km/sec and 0°.

Like other composites [5], internal damage in the RCC substrate can extend significantly beyond the external damage that is readily detected by visual observation. Internal damage in the RCC, consisting of micro-cracks and delaminations, can be assessed by nondestructive evaluation (NDE). Ultrasonic and X-ray NDE techniques were applied to the RCC samples. Figure 5 illustrates both visible exterior damage and the internal damage revealed by ultrasonic C-Scan to the RCC tested in JSC HIT-F Shot 2043. The C-Scan area of 26 mm x 20 mm is approximately twice the diameter of the coating damage (or ~15 times the projectile diameter).

Figure 5. JSC HIT-F Shot 2043: 1.59 mm Al 2017T4 projectile at 5.03 km/sec and 65°.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

A set of equations was developed correlating RCC damage to impact conditions (projectile size, speed, impact angle, density). A correlation relating penetration depth, P (cm), into the coated RCC as a function of projectile parameters was developed from the HVI data, as follows:

$$P = 0.61 d (V \cos \Theta)^{2/3} (\rho_p / \rho_t)^{0.5} \quad (1)$$

This equation is based on HVI tests with aluminum and lower density projectiles at impact speeds above 5 km/sec for the specific type of RCC tested. The velocity scaling in Equation 1 is based on previously developed penetration equations for single-sheet monolithic or laminated materials [6-8]. The equation should not be applied for impact speeds less than 5 km/sec, or for projectiles with densities greater than aluminum. Figure 6 compares the HVI data in Table 1 with the predicted penetration depth from Equation 1. Generally, there is a good agreement with the aluminum and nylon impact data. However, Equation 1 underpredicts the penetration from low-speed (~2.5 km/sec) steel projectiles by a factor of 2 or more. Additional tests will further explore penetration by high density projectiles.

Figure 6. RCC HVI Penetration Data (comparison between predicted penetration depth by Equation 1 and experimental results)

The RCC thickness, t (cm), to prevent complete penetration is given in Equation 2. The RCC samples become completely penetrated (perforated) as projectile size and/or velocity increases, because the growing front-side crater and rear-side spall meet. Thus, the required thickness to prevent perforation is significantly greater than the penetration depth calculated by Equation 1.

$$t = 2.3 * P \text{ \{thickness to prevent complete penetration\}} \quad (2)$$

The RCC must be substantially thicker than that calculated by Equation 2 to prevent rear-side spall as given in Equation 3:

$$t = 4.5 * P \text{ \{thickness to prevent rear-side spall\}} \quad (3)$$

For aluminum projectiles impacting the 6.3 mm thick RCC samples predominately tested in this study, the following damage thresholds were established as a function of the projectile's normal component kinetic energy (the specified damage mode occurs above the given kinetic energy):

Damage Mode	Normal Component Projectile Kinetic Energy Range (J)
(B) Complete Penetration of SiC Coating	1 to 2.5
(C) Rear-Side Spall	4 to 7
(D) Complete Penetration of RCC Sample	30 to 50

The kinetic energy range (minimum and maximum) accounts for the range in possible impact conditions causing threshold damage, and variations in target parameters such as coating thickness (0.5 mm to 1.0 mm) which influences the threshold damage conditions.

Figure 7 illustrates the impact conditions causing complete coating penetration (damage mode B in Figure 2), rear side spall (damage mode C), and complete penetration of the RCC (damage mode D) from the HVI test data. The vertical dotted lines in Figure 7 define the regions where the various types of RCC damage in Figure 2 occur for aluminum and nylon projectiles.

Figure 7. RCC Damage Thresholds.

6. THEORETICAL DISCUSSION

The JSC HIT-F utilizes analytical models and numerical codes to gain insights into HVI effects on spacecraft structures [4]. Computer simulations of HIT-F Shot 2316 (0.8 mm aluminum projectile at 6.84 km/sec and 0°) were performed at the HIT-F using the CTH Eulerian hydrocode from Sandia National Laboratories [9]. The hydrocode calculations were made with averaged bulk properties for the carbon substrate and SiC coating. Although the actual orthotropic nature of the RCC was not modeled in the calculations, the simulation demonstrated that many observed features of HVI into complex structures such as RCC are successfully modeled.

The CTH results of the simulation are illustrated in a series of plots contained in Figure 8 encompassing 2825 computational cycles and 20 μsec of the impact event. The plots are read from left to right starting on the top left. Each plot is divided in half with the location of projectile/target materials as a function of time on the right, and the pressure wave propagation on the left. There are eight pressure contours in units of dyne/cm² ranging from the material spall limits to 10¹² dyne/cm² (1 Mbar). The plot axes units are in centimeters. The simulation time is indicated in the lower right-hand corner of each plot frame.

ZDC Block 1 X (cm)
 Shot 2316,0.079cmP,6.84km/s,0.635cmT,RCC/SIC
 BSQDSX G 2/19/93 16:41:59 CTH 0 Time=0.

ZDC Block 1 X (cm)
 Shot 2316,0.079cmP,6.84km/s,0.635cmT,RCC/SIC
 BSQDTW 2/19/93 16:43:52 CTH 181 Time=6.06154x10⁻⁷

ZDC Block 1 X (cm)
 Shot 2316,0.079cmP,6.84km/s,0.635cmT,RCC/SIC
 BSQDTW 2/19/93 16:55:54 CTH 301 Time=1.4008x10⁻⁶

ZDC Block 1 X (cm)
 Shot 2316,0.079cmP,6.84km/s,0.635cmT,RCC/SIC
 BSQDTW 2/19/93 17:35:50 CTH 456 Time=2.50048x10⁻⁶

ZDC Block 1 X (cm)
 Shot 2316,0.079cmP,6.84km/s,0.635cmT,RCC/SIC
 BSQDTW 2/19/93 20:07:26 CTH 1478 Time=1.00024x10⁻⁵

ZDC Block 1 X (cm)
 Shot 2316,0.079cmP,6.84km/s,0.635cmT,RCC/SIC
 BSQDTW 2/19/93 22:38:43 CTH 2825 Time=2.00063x10⁻⁵

Figure 8. CTH Hydrocode Simulation of JSC HIT-F Shot 2316 (at time=0, 0.6 μ sec, 1.4 μ sec, 2.5 μ sec, 10 μ sec, and 20 μ sec after impact).

A maximum hydrodynamic pressure of 580 kbar occurs at the point of impact. Because the interface between the SiC coating and RCC substrate partially reflects the impact shock wave, the top of the RCC substrate only reaches 80 kbar. The initial impact induced compressive wave reaches the back side of the composite target at about 1.4 μ sec. Separation of the RCC and SiC layers (both top and bottom) starts to occur at about 2.5 μ sec. The bottom SiC coating fully separates at about 4 μ sec and continues to move away from the RCC. Internal fracturing of the RCC begins to occur at 4.5 μ sec when tensile stresses exceed the material fracture stress. A comparison between test data and simulation results follows:

	<u>Shot 2316</u>	<u>CTH Simulation</u>
Penetration Depth (mm)	2.02	2.06
Front Exposed RCC Size (mm)	3.8 x 3.5	4.1 (diameter)
Front SiC Coating Damage Size (mm)	9.9 x 9.6	10.4 (diameter)
Back Exposed RCC Size (mm)	5.5 x 4.9	5.6 (diameter)

7. CONCLUSIONS

Correlations have been derived by analysis of data from HVI tests on coated RCC samples that are suitable for predicting the depth of penetration into RCC by aluminum and lower density projectiles, and for determining the required RCC thickness to prevent perforation and rear-side spall. In addition, projectile kinetic energy ranges were determined that would result in different levels of damage to the RCC such as complete penetration of the surface coating, detached spall from the rear side of the RCC, and threshold perforation of the RCC. Simulations of the impact event indicated that the SiC coatings act to lower the impact stresses in the RCC substrate, thereby reducing internal damage.

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